

Studies in the Complexes of Anthrones with Metal Halides: Part VII. Heats of Reaction of Boron and Aluminium Halides with Anthrones

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Heats of reaction of boron and aluminium chlorides and bromides with anthrone, 10-benzalanthrone and 10, 10-dibenzylanthrone have been measured in *o*-dichlorobenzene. The following relative orders of acceptor and donor strengths of the reacting species have been inferred;

and

It has been reported that boron chloride and bromide form 1 : 1 complexes with anthrone, 10-benzalanthrone and 10, 10-dibenzylanthrone whereas aluminium chloride and bromide yield 1 : 1 adducts with benzalanthrone. Aluminium chloride and bromide only change the colour of benzene solutions of anthrone and dibenzylanthrone but no compound could be isolated¹. In the present communication, heats of reaction of these anthrones with boron and aluminium chlorides and bromides have been measured in *o*-dichlorobenzene with a view to ascertain the relative orders of acceptor strength of these halides and the donor strength of the anthrones.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Heats of reaction were measured in an isothermal phase change calorimeter controlled at 26.9°. The experimental details have been described in an earlier publication². The reactions have been carried out in *o*-dichlorobenzene medium, Lewis acid being taken in excess. The results obtained have been presented in Table I. The maximum probable error has been less than 1%.

TABLE I

Heats of reaction of boron and aluminium halides with anthrones in o-dichlorobenzene.

Lewis acid	Heat of reaction (kcal/mole)		
	Anthrone	Benzalanthrone	Dibenzylanthrone
BCl ₃	46.9	33.1	—
BBr ₃	49.4	47.8	43.3
AlCl ₃	19.1	22.1	15.9
AlBr ₃	40.8	32.8	21.5

1. R. C. Paul, Ram Parkash and S. S. Sandhu, *Z. anorg. Allgem. Chem.*, 1967, **352**, 322.
2. R. C. Paul, Ram Parkash, S. C. Ahluwalia and S. S. Sandhu, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 373.

DISCUSSION

In the present studies *o*-dichlorobenzene has been used as a solvent for thermochemical studies. Heats of solution of antimony (V) and tin (IV) chlorides in this solvent have been found to be 3.8 and 1.9 kcal/mole respectively. In comparison with solvents such as dimethylformamide, ethyl acetate, methanol, ethanol and acetic acid, it is far more inert as is evident from the heats of solution of these Lewis acids in these polar solvents which vary between 24–44 kcal/mole³. However, it is slightly more reactive than carbon tetrachloride as the heats of solution of antimony (V) and tin (IV) chlorides are 0.04 and 0.51–3.38 kcal/mole respectively⁴. These values indicate that *o*-dichlorobenzene is not a very inert solvent.

Heats of reaction of boron chloride and bromide with anthrones indicate that boron bromide is a stronger Lewis acid than the corresponding chloride towards these ketones. Similar order of acceptor strengths of boron halides has already been reported in literature^{2, 5-7}.

Heats of reaction of aluminium chloride and bromide with anthrone are 19.1 and 40.8 kcal/mole, with benzanthrone 22.1 and 32.8 kcal/mole and with dibenzylanthrone 15.9 and 21.5 kcal/mole respectively. The following order of acceptor strength of aluminium halides may, therefore, be inferred;

The above order is supported by heat of solution of these halides in nitrobenzene⁸, their heats of reaction with benzanthrone², benzaldehyde¹⁰, acetophenone and benzophenone^{9, 11}, heat of formation of their ionic complexes with alkali metal halides¹² and infra-red spectral studies of their adducts with acetophenone¹³ and ethyl acetate⁷.

It is, therefore, established that the bromides of boron and aluminium are better acceptors than the corresponding chlorides, though an opposite order is expected on the basis of electronegativity and steric requirements of the halogens. The reasons for this have been discussed in an earlier communication².

It is evident from the present studies that boron halides are stronger Lewis acids than the corresponding aluminium halides. The observation is supported by heat of complex formation of boron and aluminium halides with benzanthrone² and infra-red spectral studies of the adducts of these halides with ethyl acetate. Similarly, infra-red spectra of xanthone

3. S. C. Ahluwalia, Ph.D. Thesis, Panjab University, Chandigarh, 1966.
4. R. C. Paul, M. L. Lakhanpal, P. S. Gill and J. Singh, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 262.
5. N. N. Greenwood and P. G. Perkins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1141, 1145.
6. D. Cook, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1963, **41**, 522.
7. M. F. Lappert, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 542.
8. V. A. Plotnikov and R. G. Vaisberg, *Zapiski Inst. Khim., Akad. Nauk, USSR*, 1940, **7**, 71; C.A., 1941, **35**, 2405.
9. M. H. Dilke and D. D. Eley and (Miss) M. G. Sheppard, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1950, **46**, 261.
10. M. H. Dilke and D. D. Eley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2601.
11. N. N. Lebedev, *Zhur. Obshchei Khim.*, 1951, **21**, 1788; C.A., 1952, **46**, 6586b.
12. V. A. Plotnikov and S. I. Yakubson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, **12**, 113.
13. B. P. Susz and P. Chalandon, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1958, **41**, 1332.

complexes with boron and aluminium bromide⁶ and nuclear magnetic resonance spectra of the adducts of these chlorides with dimethylformamide¹⁴ lend further support to the above order.

The measurements of heat of reaction suggests the following relative order of decreasing donor strength of these anthrones with respect to boron and aluminium chlorides and bromides;

A similar order has been proposed on the basis of heats of complex formation of these anthrones with tin (IV) and antimony (V) chlorides in benzene². The capacity of these anthrones to form adducts with various metal halides, infra-red spectral studies and thermogravimetric analyses of the complexes formed^{1,15} are in keeping with the above order. Since dibenzylanthrone is a weaker donor than benzalanthronone which in turn is weaker than anthrone, it is evident, therefore, that the additional benzene rings act as electron sinks and thus reduce the donor strength of benzalanthronone and dibenzylanthrone.

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14. S. J. Kuhn and J. S. McIntyre, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1965, **43**, 375.
15. R. C. Paul, Ram Parkash and S. S. Sandhu, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 426; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1907; 1967, **29**, 1915.